

RI4C2
Research & Innovation
For Cities & Citizens

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FOREU2 Coordination: Setup of thematic sub- groups

Short communication (report)

DELIVERABLE 50
MONTH 1

The 24 alliances from the second Erasmus+ Pilot call (ATHENA, AURORA Alliance, Circle U, E3UDRES2, EC2U, EELISA, ENGAGE.EU, ENHANCE, ENLIGHT, ERUA, EUNICE, EUNIWell, EURECA-PRO, EuroTeQ, Eut, FILMEU, INVEST, NeurotechEU, RUN-EU, T4E, ULYSSEUS, UNIC, UNITA, UNIVERSEH) have agreed, in their SwafS application documents, that they will ensure joint collaboration across their SwafS projects by creating a “Forum of European Universities 2 – FOREU2” where they will discuss and share good practices concerning R&I. The EC2U Alliance is the coordinator of FOREU2, and also will ensure the dialogue with the Alliance in charge of the FOREU1 (ECIU).

Thematic sub-groups were created according to the topics of interest discussed during consultation among the 24 alliances. Hence, FOREU2 is now composed by one “Global Forum” (composed of the 24 Alliance Coordinators) and 13 sub-groups, each chaired by a different Alliance (see list below).

Ludovic Thilly as Coordinator of the EC2U Alliance SwafS project, RI4C2, acts as Chair of the “Global Forum” and Chair of the “SwafS projects” sub-group. He also presented the network FOREU2 during the Virtual Info Session on the implementation of Horizon 2020 European University Alliances (Pilot II) organised by the European Research Executive Agency (REA) (See presentation slides in annex I).

FOREU2 structure:

- 1. Global Forum (for coordinators only):**
Chair: Ludovic Thilly from *EC2U*
- 2. Alliance coordination (operational issues):**
Chair: Gijs Coucke & Delfien Cloet from *ENLIGHT*
- 3. Education innovation and mobility (incl. new curricula & legal barriers):**
Chair: Maria Stoicheva from *Transform4Europe*
- 4. Students & staff engagement:**
Chair: Konstantinos Petridis from *ATHENA*
- 5. Citizens engagement:**
Chair: Charlotte Venema & Christophe Bruchansky from *UNIC*

6. SwafS projects:Chair: Ludovic Thilly from *EC2U***7. Legal entity/future statute (incl. governance):**Chair: Dana Samson from *CIRCLE U***8. Digital services and data sharing (incl. joint platforms):**Chair: Vlad Petcu from *UNITA***9. Cooperation with non-EU partners:**Chair: Matxalen Llosa & Magdalena Sikorska from *EUNICE***10. Higher Education Transformation Agenda:**Chair: Anne-May Janssen & Rónán O'Muirthile from *FILMEU*Co-Chair: Manuel José Damásio from *AURORA***11. Student Communities:**Chair: Lukas Redermann from *Transform4Europe*Co-Chair: Maxime Geerts from *Circle U***12. University-Industry Collaboration:**Chair: Jörgen Sjöberg from *ENHANCE***13. Quality Assurance:**Chair: Frank Wehinger & Johanna Vogt from *ERUA***14. Multilingualism:**Chair: Ramona Baumgater from *ERUA*

Note:

For details of composition and contact information of the different groups, please contact the Global Manager of RI4C2: carolina.liore@univ-poitiers.fr

Annex I

Presentation of FOREU2 during the Virtual Info Session on 25th October 2021

FOREU2 - *Forum of the 24 Alliances selected in 2020*

Presentation of FOREU2 & its SwafS sub-group

Virtual Info Session

IMPLEMENTATION OF H2020 EUROPEAN UNIVERSITIES ALLIANCES H2020-IBA-SwafS-Support-2-2020

The Lump sum approach, financial reporting and amendments

25 October 2021, 10h00-12h00

Prof. Dr. Ludovic Thilly

Executive Vice-Rector, University of Poitiers (FR)

Coordinator of the EC2U Alliance of European Universities (ec2u.eu)

Coordinator of H2020 SwafS project "RI4C2"

Coordinator of FOREU2, the Forum of 24 new European University Alliances

FOREU2

- *creation of FOREU2*

- ⇒ Initially proposed in the context of the **preparation of SwafS projects** submitted by all second-generation Alliances (Nov. 2020)
- ⇒ Each SwafS project includes the following text:

“In the same fashion as the 17 Alliances from the first Erasmus+ Pilot Call, the 24 Alliances from the second Erasmus+ Pilot Call (ATHENA, Aurora Alliance, Circle U, E3UDRES2, EC2U, EELISA, ENGAGE.EU, ENHANCE, ENLIGHT, ERUA, EUNICE, EUniWell, EURECA-PRO, EuroTeQ, Eut, FILMEU, INVEST, NeurotechEU, RUN-EU, T4E, ULYSSEUS, UNIC, UNITA, UNIVERSEH), have agreed by the time of the submission, that they will ensure joint collaboration across their SwafS projects by creating a “Forum of European Universities #2 – FOREU2” (in reference to the group of the 17 first Alliances called “FOREU”) where they will discuss and share intelligence (via regular face-to-face or on-line meetings) resulting from:

- **assessment of current and best practices and progress made (incl. success stories) in the implementation of (R&I) long-term strategies;**
- **special focus on practices and measures taken/to be taken to ensure the mainstreaming of gender dimension in R&I long-term strategies;**
- **identification of barriers – legal, financial and regulatory - whatever level at which the barriers exist (local, regional or European).”**

FOREU2

- *Anticipation of FOREU2 kick-off*

Early 2021, Coordinators from second-generation Alliances decided to **launch FOREU2 without waiting for the start of SwafS projects**

⇒ first meeting of **E+ Coordinators** on 24/02/2021

- *structure of FOREU2*

⇒ **Global Forum** (Coordinated by LT-EC2U) + **topical sub-groups** (Coordinated by other Alliances)

⇒ **Sub-group topics**

- Alliance coordination (operational issues)
- Education innovation and mobility (incl. new curricula & legal barriers)
- Students & staff engagement
- Citizens engagement
- Legal entity/future statute (incl. governance)
- Digital services and data sharing (incl. joint platforms)
- Cooperation with non-EU partners
- European Strategy for Universities
- Students communities
- Quality Assurance
- University-Industry cooperation
- **SwafS projects (to be sub-divided later, if relevant)**

FOREU2

- Meetings

- ⇒ **Global Forum meetings:** 24/02/2021, 23/03/2021, 12/05/2021, 09/06/2021, 29/06/2021, 21/09/2021 (FOREU1 & FOREU2), next meeting in Nov. 2021
- ⇒ **Topical sub-groups meetings:** most sub-groups have met once or more
- ⇒ **SwafS sub-group:**
 - * coordinated by LT-EC2U
 - * **already contacted for GEP survey**
 - * **first meeting to be scheduled in Nov. 2021**

- Deliverables

- ⇒ **FOREU2 online meetings** every 3 months (meeting minutes delivered by EC2U Alliance & its SwafS RI4C2 project)
- ⇒ **First FOREU2 report** on “practices and measures taken/to be taken to ensure the mainstreaming of gender dimension in R&I long-term strategies” - Due date: M24
- ⇒ **Second FOREU2 report** on “Collection of 24 case studies (one per Alliance) on progress made in the implementation of R&I longterm strategies, in particular via the identification and removal of legal/financial/regulatory barrier(s)” – Due date: M36

FOREU2

- *Contact info*

⇒ FOREU2 & SwafS sub-group Chair: ludovic.thilly@univ-poitiers.fr

⇒ EC2U/RI4C2 project manager: carolina.liore@univ-poitiers.fr

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